

Comparative Analysis of Efficient Face Recognition Models.

A case study of EfficientNetV2B0, NasNetMobile, DenseNet169, MobileNet V2 with Transfer Learning, L2 Regularization and Dropout.

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1. Abstract

This study presents a comparative analysis of four deep learning models, MobileNetV2, NasNetMobile, DenseNet169, and EfficientNetV2B0 applied to face recognition using transfer learning, L2 Regularization and Dropout. The primary objective is to evaluate the models accuracy and training time. MobileNetV2 demonstrates a significantly lower training time compared to other models while achieving 96% accuracy. EfficientNetV2B0, although attaining 99% accuracy, requires considerably longer training. In terms of overall efficiency, MobileNetV2 strikes the best balance between accuracy and speed. Meanwhile, EfficientNetB0, though highly accurate, necessitates hyperparameter tuning to enhance its efficiency.

CCS CONCEPTS • Computing methodologies ~ Machine learning ~ Machine learning algorithms ~ Regularization

Additional Keywords and Phrases: Face recognition, Transfer learning, Deep learning, MobileNetV2, EfficientNet, L2 Regularization, Dropout

1 INTRODUCTION

In the evolution of computer vision and artificial intelligence, face recognition is a crucial application with widespread implications in various , such as security systems, biometric authentication, and personalized user experiences. There are lots of face recognition models out there but the demand for accurate, easy-to-implement, and efficient face recognition systems grows. Despite the variety of existing models, striking a balance between high accuracy and computational efficiency remains a challenge. As deep learning continues to advance, exploring state-of-the-art models becomes essential to meeting these demands. This study investigates four leading deep learning models—MobileNetV2, NasNetMobile, DenseNet169, and EfficientNetV2B0—for face recognition, focusing on their performance in terms of accuracy, training speed, and overall efficiency.

1.1 Deep Learning

Deep learning is a subfield of artificial intelligence (AI) that involves neural networks with multiple layers (deep neural networks) to learn patterns and make intelligent decisions from data. It mimics the human brain's way of processing data for tasks like object detection, language translation, and facial recognition, often without human supervision. Its power lies in its ability to handle large amounts of unstructured data, making it invaluable in detecting fraud, identifying suspicious activity, and more. Deep Learning is been implemented in various domains to solve problems like computer vision, natural language processing, speech recognition, etc. Deep learning Includes Neural networks, Deep Architectures, Feature Learning [12], End-to-end learning [13], Scalability, Convolutional Neural network (CNN)[6], and recurrent neural networks (RNNs) [14], Etc.

1.2 CNN (Convolutional Neural Network)

Convolutional neural network (CNN) [6] is a deep learning architecture that is particularly effective for computer vision tasks like face recognition, image classification, and object detection. CNNs apply convolution operations to the input data through convolutional layers, allowing the model to learn hierarchical features, from simple edges to complex objects. This makes CNNs highly efficient in processing and understanding image data.

Figure 1: CNN architecture [Public domain] (https://cezannec.github.io/Convolutional_Neural_Networks/)

1.3 L2 Regularization

L2 Regularization [8] is also known as Ridge Regularization. It is used in machine learning and deep learning to prevent overfitting and improve the generalization of a model. Overfitting occurs when a model becomes too much complex, capturing noise. L2 Regularization adds a penalty term to the loss function. Encouraging the models to keep the weights of parameters small.

The L2 Regularization terms are added to the standard loss function, and the modified loss becomes:

$$Loss_{L2} = Loss_{Original} + 2\lambda \sum_i \omega_i^2$$

Here:

- LossOriginal is the original loss function without regularization.
- ω_i are the weights of the model.
- λ is the regularization strength, a hyperparameter that determines the importance of the regularization term.

1.4 Transfer Learning

Transfer learning [7] is a technique where a model is trained on one task but repurposed for another task. Transfer learning uses the knowledge of pre-trained weights of the first task and then improves it for another task. It provides a powerful approach to overcome challenges efficiently. It is effective when there is a limited labeled dataset available. The process of transfer learning involves pre-training, Feature extraction, and Fine tuning.

Transfer learning offers improved training speed, Better generalization, and Effectiveness in low-data scenarios.

1.5 Literature review of key architecture for face recognition

MobileNetV2 [20] is a lightweight deep-learning model architecture designed for mobile and edge devices. It was introduced as an improvement of the original MobileNet [28] architecture, It provides better performance in terms of both accuracy and efficiency, making it ideal for resource-constrained environments.

NasNetMobile [21] (Neural Architecture Search Network Mobile) is a neural network architecture designed for mobile and edge devices. It is part of the Neural Architecture Search (NAS) [29] family of models. The architecture is not manually designed by human experts but is instead discovered automatically through a search process.

DenseNet169 [10] employs dense connections between layers. This lets the network reuse features, improves gradient overflow, and leads to highly efficient networks that perform well in tasks such as image classification and feature learning.

EfficientNetV2B0 [3] stands out for its compound scaling, simultaneously adjusting depth, width, and resolution for optimal performance. This model is both highly accurate and computationally efficient, making it suitable for a variety of computer vision tasks.

1.6 Our Purpose

These architectures contributed outstandingly to computer vision, However, their specific effectiveness in face recognition when using transfer learning, L2 Regularization, Dropout, and limited training data remains an for further exploration. This study aims to evaluate and compare these models under such conditions.

2. Models

2.1 MobileNetV2

MobileNetV2 is an advancement of the original MobileNet architecture [28], with the key difference being the use of inverted residual blocks and bottleneck features. This modification significantly reduces the parameter count while maintaining performance. MobileNetV2 is highly versatile, supporting any input size larger than 32x32, with larger

input sizes providing better accuracy. Its lightweight design makes it ideal for mobile and edge devices.

Figure 2: MobileNetV2 architecture [28],

2.2 NasNetMobile

NasNet [21] introduces a method to learn the model architectures directly on the dataset of interest. As this approach can be computationally expensive for large datasets, NasNet [21] propose to search for an architectural building block on a small dataset and then transfer the block to a larger dataset. The key contribution of this work is the design of a new search space called the “NASNet search space, which enables the transferability of learned structures across datasets.

Figure 3: NasNetMobile Architecture [21]

2.3 DenseNet169

DenseNet169, a variant of the DenseNet architecture [10] is designed to facilitate feature reuse and improve gradient flow. DenseNet connects each layer to every other layer in a feed-forward fashion, enhancing efficiency and reducing the number of parameters. Bottleneck layers (using 1x1 and 3x3 convolutions) reduce dimensionality, while transition layers control spatial dimensions through 1x1 convolutions and average pooling. DenseNet is recognized for its high accuracy and parameter efficiency, particularly in image classification tasks.

Figure 4: DenseNet architecture [10]

2.4 EfficientNetV2B0

EfficientNetV2B0 [3] aims to achieve high accuracy while being computationally efficient. Its innovative approach to model scaling the depth, width, and resolution of the network is scaled simultaneously to find an optimal balance between performance and computational efficiency. EfficientNetB0 uses depthwise separable convolutions and inverted residuals with linear bottlenecks, similar to MobileNetV2, to reduce parameters while maintaining performance. This architecture has demonstrated state-of-the-art results on several benchmark datasets.

Figure 5: EfficientNet Model Scaling architecture [3]

2.5 Our Work

In our work, We begin a comprehensive investigation for time efficiency, easy-to-implement, and accurate face recognition systems for limited custom datasets. The aforementioned state-of-the-art models —MobileNetV2, NasNetMobile, DenseNet169, and EfficientNetV2B0—were selected as the foundation for our research.

Our work focuses on using the power of transfer learning with L2 Regularization [8] to fine-tune these models for face recognition. The primary objective is to determine which model provides the most favorable performance on our custom, small-scale face recognition dataset, considering both accuracy and training efficiency.

3. Experiment set

In this section, we discuss the components and processes involved in developing our model using a deep learning approach. The dataset was created by collecting images from random individuals. The models MobileNetV2, NasNetMobile, DenseNet169, and EfficientNetV2B0 were applied to the face recognition task. Each model was evaluated using metrics such as training and validation accuracy, training and validation loss, and epoch times.

Figure 6 Dataset

3.1 Data

The dataset for this research consists of 174 images of 3 individual faces with various backgrounds, lightning, and expression. The image sizes were not uniform and were adjusted accordingly during preprocessing.

Pre-processing: The MTCNN [1] face detection model was employed to detect and crop faces from all the images. After detection, the images were organized into three folders, one for each individual. The dataset was split into training and validation sets using an 80:20 ratio. Input image sizes were set based on the requirements of each model.

Data augmentation: To improve the generalization of the models, we applied various data augmentation techniques, including rescaling, shearing, zooming, and flipping the images randomly using Python.

4 Result and discussion

In this section, the outcomes of the experiments using the methods discussed previously. The Author use a similar approach to all models, using the same learning rate [15], batch size [24], one hot encoding [23], data augmentation [25], optimizer [26], epoch, Dynamic Learning Rate Tuning [22], loss function [27], The performance of each model was evaluated on the test set based on accuracy. Accuracy is defined as the ratio of correct predictions to the total number of faces in the dataset, multiplied by 100%.

Accuracy Formula:

$$Accuracy = \left(\frac{Correct\ prediction}{total\ data} \right) \times 100\%$$

4.1 MobileNet V2

Figure 7: training and validation accuracy of the MobileNet V2 model.

Figure 8: training and validation loss of the MobileNet V2 model.

We froze all layers initially and trained the MobileNetV2 model. The training accuracy reached 99.6%, while validation accuracy was 96%. Training loss decreased steadily, reaching 0.87, and validation loss reached 0.95. The total number of epochs was 150, with an average epoch time of 8 seconds. Due to the strong performance, we did not unfreeze any additional layers for further training.

4.2 NasNetMobile

Figure 9: training and validation accuracy of the NasNetMobile model.

Figure 10: training and validation loss of the NasNetMobile model.

Initially, we froze the top layers of NasNetMobile [3] and trained the model using the same techniques. The performance was inconsistent, with a per-epoch time averaging 11 seconds. Training accuracy reached 99.7%, but validation accuracy was 92%. The training loss was 1.03, and validation loss was 1.32.

Next, we unfroze all top layers and retrained the model using the weights from the previous training.

Figure 11: unfreezing all the layers and training and validation accuracy of the NasNetMobile.

Figure 12: unfreezing all the layers and training and validation loss of the NasNetMobile.

After unfreezing all top layers and retraining, the performance improved significantly. Training accuracy remained stable at 99.7%, and validation accuracy improved to 92%. Validation and training losses were 2.04 and 2.23, respectively. The total number of epochs was 150, with an average epoch time of 40 seconds.

4.5 DenseNet169

Figure 13: training and validation accuracy of the DenseNet169 model.

Figure 14: training and validation loss of the DenseNet169 model.

We trained DenseNet169 by freezing the top layers. The training accuracy reached 99.6%, with validation accuracy at 96%. Training loss reduced over time to 0.620, and validation loss decreased to 0.777. The total number of epochs was 150, with an average epoch time of 20 seconds. Given the satisfactory results, we did not unfreeze the top layers for further retraining.

4.6 EfficientNetV2B0

Figure 15: training and validation accuracy of the EfficientNetV2B0 model.

Figure 16: training and validation loss of the EfficientNetV2B0 model.

Initially, EfficientNetV2B0 [3] was trained using the same techniques. The average epoch time was 14 seconds, but initial performance was poor, with training accuracy at 40% and validation accuracy at 36%. Training and validation losses were 1.101 and 1.1156, respectively.

Next, we unfroze all top layers and retrained the model with the same weights.

Figure 17: unfreezing all the layers and training and validation accuracy of the EfficientNetV2B0.

Figure 18: unfreezing all the layers, training and validation loss of the EfficientNetV2B0.

After unfreezing the layers, the model's performance improved considerably. Training accuracy reached 99.7%, and validation accuracy improved to 99.2%. The losses for training and validation decreased to 1.781 and 1.782, respectively. Increasing the number of epochs could potentially reduce the losses further. The total number of epochs was 150, with an average epoch time of 30 seconds.

4.7 Model Performance Table

Table 1: Performance comparison of models.

S/L	Model Name	Accuracy	Avg Per Epoch Time
1	MobileNetV2	96%	8s
2	NasNetMobile	92%	40s
3	DenseNet169	96%	20s
4	EfficientNetV2B0	99.2%	30s

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we implemented a face recognition system using existing deep learning models with transfer learning, L2 Regularization, and Dropout techniques, trained on a small dataset. Among the models, MobileNetV2 and EfficientNetV2B0 performed the best in our experiments.

MobileNetV2 achieved 96% accuracy with a per-epoch training time of just 8 seconds, making it efficient and fast to train. EfficientNetV2B0, although delivering a higher accuracy of 99%, required significantly more training time due to its complexity. Achieving this accuracy involved extensive hyperparameter tuning and retraining.

Overall, MobileNetV2 demonstrated a strong balance of speed and performance, making it a more practical option for face recognition tasks in environments where computational resources are limited. Our research not only provides valuable insights into the comparative performance of deep learning models for face recognition but also highlights the importance of transfer learning, L2 Regularization, Dropout, and dynamic learning rate tuning techniques in improving recognition accuracy, particularly on custom datasets.

5.1 Future Work

In future work, we plan to test MobileNetV2 with ArcFace [11] to evaluate its performance on a small dataset. Additionally, we aim to develop a face recognition system that could be applied to IoT-based security systems, access control systems, and other real-world applications requiring accurate and efficient facial recognition.

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